

Soup on Mona Lisa

Latest attack on the world's most famous painting

Alex Weissel

On January 28th 2024, two women belonging to the group “Riposte Alimentaire”, loosely translated as “Food Response”, decided to throw their anger on the face of Mona Lisa, in the form of a French gourmet delicacy — pumpkin soup. Their motif, apparently, was summed up in a shouted statement:

“What is more important? Art or the right to a healthy and sustainable diet?”

It seems that, in their minds at least, one renaissance masterpiece and Louvre’s greatest asset is somehow related to the ongoing French government’s issues regarding food production and exports, yet glossing over the fact they wasted food in the process. We can safely assume that Leonardo da Vinci did not have sustainability, organic nutrition or veganism on his mind in the course of 16 years it took him to complete the painting (cca 1503-1516). This event, regrettably, was not the first strike against La Gioconda, nor an isolated attack on fine arts during the past years. The soup incident was in fact No.6, excluding the theft of 1911. It is the cardinal reason why *the most famous painting in the world* remained encased in protective glass since 1956, after suffering a hit from a rock. What makes this latest and penultimate event from 2022 specific; when a 36 year old man pretending to be disabled attempted to break the glass, subsequently smearing cake over the transparent surface; is that they were not enacted out of personal motivations, unlike prior, but rather as a part of “green activism”— Individuals and organizations who claim to fight for the benefit of Earth and Humanity, by inflicting damage to the only true value humanity could ever leave behind — Art.

Good news is that Mona Lisa was not “blessed” by the soup, as the bullet proof glass performed its task immaculately. And even if it hadn’t, the actual painting would have staid safe, for what’s displayed in “La Salle des Etats” is most probably one of several high-end copies. Even though the original masterpiece went through numerous cycles of restoration and conservation, canvas and colour can only last so long, especially when exposed to fluctuations of temperature, humidity and constant illumination. Da Vinci’s La Gioconda is safely stored in a controlled environment, far away from millions of tourists and occasional “green warriors”.

The question that remains is why would anyone want to mar a piece of art, thus forcing it into a showcase for their socio-political fight, especially if the art in question has no connection with it? This goes beyond vandalism, for the act itself is perceived to have some meaning. The most common answer we hear is shock value, or getting attention. We live in an age of mass media presence and violent communication. Yet, throwing pumpkin soup on a politician, social stakeholder, government entity or manager of a corporation, all involved in France’s ongoing food crisis, would have made more sense, whilst generating equal publicity. Nevertheless, “green activists” are well aware of such acts having serious legal and financial repercussions. A 500 year old painting remains passive and submissive. It will not complain nor throw a lawsuit. It is simply easier to vent frustration on someone or something that cannot fight back, even if this something represents the very best humanity has inherited. Even though the “Food Response” perpetrators have been apprehended, chances are they are to be released with a symbolic fine. This brings us to a rather grim reality — Upcoming generations will build, or rather re-purpose the world on the ashes of their own heritage. And while this is not the first nor last time such transitions took place throughout history, a dreary future lingers. After all this time we haven’t learned from our mistakes. One could argue we’ve gone from bad to worse, for art was one of few things coveted and treasured even in times of war and destruction. Will we ever learn?

Is Mona Lisa Overrated?

Contemporary opinions propel the idea of Mona Lisa being overrated as the world’s greatest masterpiece. This comes as a result of her over saturated presence in public; a phenomenon reinforced by mass media, consumerism and modern art alike. Saying you like La Gioconda is interpreted as a worn out cliché; something coming from a clueless unenlightened simpleton. But is this reputation really deserved?

Leonardo Da Vinci saw Mona Lisa as his most significant achievement, working on her for the last 16 years of his life, taking her along anywhere he went. What started as a commissioned portrait of Lisa Gherardini; a daughter of impoverished nobility who married a rich merchant Francesco del Giocondo in 1495; has grown to become not only a life-long obsession with perfection, but a comprehensive artistic experiment and a vehicle for all the painter’s skills. One of the examples is the use of *La Imprimatura* — a base of lead white on which Leonardo subsequently applied up to 30 micron-thin layers of paint, thus achieving a translucent effect with immaculate transitions and contrasts. He also pioneered the use of *Chiaroscuro* and *Sfumato* techniques on Mona Lisa, all to

create a unique life-like impression. Her mystical smile is what comes out as a jewel in his crown of skills.

Perhaps the greatest misconception about Mona Lisa insinuates that her popularity came only after the theft of 1911. Vincenzo Perugia, an Italian emigrant living in France, decided to take her off the walls of Louvre. Unlike modern “activists” however, his motifs were to bring the painting back to its initial country of origin — Italy; an act he perceived as patriotic rather than shocking. The painting was recovered, Perugia arrested, yet in the meantime, thousands of curious spectators lined up to get the glimpse of an empty place where the masterpiece once stood. The crime wasn’t noticed for an entire day, thus supporting speculations nobody really cared. However, the reason for this lied in the fact Louvre was in the process of cataloguing its collection. Both the staff and visitors simply assumed that Mona Lisa was taken down for this purpose. The truth is, she was already the most famous item on display by that time. Her engravings and photos were sold as souvenirs for decades prior, whereas numerous writers and art critics prized her beauty. Napoleon, the most powerful man in Europe, had her hanging in his bedroom. The theft only cemented La Gioconda’s reputation of being an unprecedented masterpiece, turning her into a culture icon.

Is Mona Lisa the most important painting in the world? It is hard to say. Art remains, after all, a question of perception. Nonetheless, her overall significance as humanity’s heritage is undisputed. As such, appreciation and respect is the least we can give, for the sake of ourselves and our descendants alike.

Art is the mirror of soul. Splashing soup will hardly make the world a better place.

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